

THE NEED FOR INCREASING THE COMPETENCE OF MANAGING STAFF AT A NEW STAGE OF DEVELOPMENT OF UZBEKISTAN

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Annotation: This article analyzes the priorities for improving the competence of management staff in Uzbekistan, as well as the work done in recent years in this area. Also, a model of professional competencies of civil servants was studied comparatively, and practical proposals and recommendations for improving the competence of management staff in Uzbekistan were developed.

Key words: management staff, management staff, management competencies, management capacity, management skills, modernization, qualification of personnel, social system, competence, "public service", industrialization, liberalization, democratic methods, innovation, interinformational processes, political rights and socio-political balance.

In the conditions of the new Uzbekistan, it was established as one of the important tasks to communicate with the solution by forming a compact and professional public administration system that meets modern requirements on the principle of "directing the activities of state governing bodies to serve citizens", improving the effectiveness of decision-making in the activities of state bodies and introducing innovative methods of solving This is a sign that the system of Public Administration in Uzbekistan has begun a new stage of its development. "In order to further expand private initiatives in this regard, to open up new prospects for them, it is now time to move from "Hand Management" – to systematic management, which works for a clear result." One of the important tasks before us today is the need to develop mechanisms for the formation of a reliable, effective system of public services, the direction of the administrative, organizational, political and legal foundations of the clear definition of the task, powers and responsibility of each governing unit in democratization of public management processes to the outcome.

In particular, with the Declaration of itself as a social state, the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan in the new edition undertakes to create conditions for each citizen to live a decent life..

New principles, such as building a new state, restoring international relations, opening up to the world, not returning from the path of integration with the international community, establishing new jurisdiction in the management of the state and society, developing a well-thought-out plan of action in all areas, make such demands.

The reforms carried out in the last few years were carried out directly by our President Shavkat Mirziyoev. The priority tasks set out in the strategy of action on the five priority areas of development of the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2017 — 2021, adopted by the initiative of Mirziyoev, as well as the deep study and adoption of the necessary aspects of the self-justified international experience of modern democratic state-building, which will successfully and sustainably develop in the implementation of program tasks aimed at reform and renewal.

One example of this is 1.2 of the priority direction of improving the system of state and community construction of the strategy of action on the five priority areas of development of the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2017-2021. The section is dedicated to the "reform of the public administration system", which sets out the task of reforming the public administration and the public service system by decentralizing Public Administration, increasing the level of professional training, material and social security of "civil servants, and gradually reducing state participation in the regulation of the economy."

The desire to understand the elements of any modern socio-political process, in particular such a system as public administration, motivates us to turn to the nature and essence of this issue. Many social political processes that occur in society arise precisely in close connection with the issue of governance. In fact, the Latin term "administratio" "service" and "management" denote leadership (to someone, to something). Management is a necessity, it will not be possible to direct the activities of those without management towards the goal, to develop the relevant areas. Where there is no control, chaos, dizziness will certainly occur.

In the history of political and legal teachings, it is precisely such concepts as "state", "society", management that we witness, firstly, the socio-political situation prevailing in each time, and secondly, the appeal of various criteria as a basis. In particular, it was this form of government that determined who and how the state carries out its government in an organized society.

The Great scholar Husayn preacher Koshifiy also noted that "the state and society cannot be imagined without politics, without management, because without these it is impossible to carry out the task of regulating important affairs of the world, the absence of laws on upbringing and punishment leads to a violation of state activity", "politics is necessary for the management of the country, it is not If the policy is fair, the country, society will develop, the people will live comfortably." According to The Thinker, in the absence of governance in society, elates such as humiliation and violence will rise. At the same time spoke about two visions of management, namely the control of one's own soul and the control of subordinates. In this, management is a factor of influence on consciousness, human behavior, behavior, activity by stimulating this concept, and not the use of power, relying only on administrative power. Management acquires this creativity, creativity, practical cooperation and directs the development of society.

One of the most important criteria determining the effectiveness of management is the level of confidence of the population living in a particular area in political power. Such confidence is measured by the appeals of the population to the state authorities in the social, economic, cultural, educational and domestic spheres, and their resolution, that is, their implementation. After all, the final result of management efficiency is directly reflected in the growth of the living well-being of the population.

At this point, the first level of management, the theory of management, consisting of a complex of philosophical, political, economic and sociological concepts, in which institutions are able to accurately explain the mechanism of activity in various evolutions of the development of the state and society;

-the second level of management, the sum of the various objects of management, as a unit of practical knowledge and skills, in order to ensure the progress of society, as a Applied

Science covering fundamental scientific theories (mathematics, logic, political psychology, management, acmeology).

Public administration is the practical, organizational and regulatory influence of the state on the social life activities of people, being a set of methods of legal organization of state power.

In the conditions of the new Uzbekistan, not only state bodies, but also NGOs and other institutions of civil society act as an important factor in the implementation of reforms in our society, such as the provision of effective public services to the population and the principle of a "nationalistic state".

Therefore, the fact that civil society institutions act as a kind of "partnership dialogue" between society and the state, taking into account the interests of each individual, plays an important role in increasing the contribution of legitimacy to the active civil position in humans and the activities of state bodies.

At the present stage, it is required to continue to increase the level of state governing bodies in Uzbekistan in the following directions:

- further optimization of the public administration system, effective continuation of decentralization in public administration;
- increase the professionalism and competence of Public Administration personnel based on the requirements of the present time, continuously, regularly increasing the potential of creative, personal and professional knowledge;
- Consistent and systematic implementation of reforms and measures established in the new administrative reform concept;
- restriction of interference of state bodies in the economy, including entrepreneurial activity, activities of political parties;
- deepening market reforms, introduction of effective system and mechanisms of state management of property, improvement of corporate governance;
- when modernizing public administration, serious attention should be paid to its spiritual and cultural aspects. Therefore, we agree that it is necessary to form a modern culture of administrative management in the country, as well as management USLS based on popular confidence.

With this, it can be noted that the main component of the evolution development of Public Administration is, first of all, the belief in society in it, and this trust is a factor of the correct distribution of opportunities and resources for strengthening social stability and developing effective managerial innovations in all aspects of society.

The Republic of Uzbekistan, which has the main goal of building a just humane, democratic state, a free and prosperous life, today, the implementation of its modern methods aimed at achieving tangible results in public administration, in particular, "the people should serve our people, not government agencies. After all, our people should see positive changes in their lives not tomorrow or in the distant future, but precisely today!". on the way to bringing to life the grandiose idea embedded in humanism, our President Sh. Mirziyoev is implementing solid reforms in our country.

As such, the attitude of the state to the duty and responsibility of society, its salvation, spiritual and moral image strongly influence the image of the state, the sustainable development of society through it. In this regard, the civil service is such an activity that its results cannot be exceeded by the amount or volume of documents prepared and received by

the servants, by the time spent on their work. The civil service was a kind of social attitude, in which the state authorities carried out their social processes, the function of organizing and managing human activities and activities.

The management staff in all directions, as our president noted, "...now each of us is required, first of all, to deeply understand that the task of the heads of Public Administration is to ensure the responsible performance of the tasks assigned to us on the basis of a critical assessment of the state of affairs in the areas and industries in which we are responsible, and to act selflessly in the path of this goal.

If we analyze the result of the reforms carried out above, then at a new stage of development of Uzbekistan, systematic work is being carried out in the field of Public Administration. As our President Sh. Mirziyoev noted, "every leader changes his way of working, taking into account the capabilities and skills of ordinary people, and practical projects will have a faster result if they are done." That is, it is necessary that each modern leader in his activities develops not only professional competencies, but also managerial competencies.

In conclusion, public administration is a reflection of the activities of the implementation of a unified state power with an executive focus. Such governance is represented in the first, by its focus on the introduction of basic laws, presidential decrees and decisions into life. In addition, to ensure the execution of these legal acts, state agencies have state power vaults and determine the implementation of the guidelines that must be fulfilled on behalf of the state authorities.

At the same time, the main managerial tasks of the state are to make decisions, regulate its structure and activities, ensure the safety of citizens, create favorable conditions for their comprehensive functioning, in order to maintain leadership, coordination, organization, Control, Order and develop the state in every possible way.

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